

FORGING PROCESS OF METAL MATRIX COMPOSITES REINFORCED WITH PARTICLES

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ABSTRACT

Some of the parts produced nowadays for the automotive industry are manufactured by forging. This is well understood when working with the usual materials, but it presents big problems with MMC materials.

In order to obtain a relationship between properties and forging parameters, forging tests on the 2014 aluminium alloy, reinforced with alumina particles, have been developed ranging from 400 to 520 °C, with strain rates between 5 and 0.5 sec⁻¹. Total strain produced was selected in order to study the initiation of cracks in the specimens. Optimum forging parameters have been obtained from the testing procedure.

Keywords: forging, forgeability, metal matrix composites, compression tests.

1. INTRODUCTION

Metal Matrix Composites are acknowledged as materials with good applications in the automotive industry in the near future. Their capacity to stand high temperatures while maintaining good properties, in addition to lightness and abrasion resistance, which can be achieved by a good selection of matrix and reinforcement, has suggested possible applications for this group of materials in automotive components.

There are some enterprises who seem to have an efficient process and are trading MMC semi-products, aluminium based, with silicon carbide or alumina as reinforcement. The materials they sell are produced by casting techniques, such as gravity and discontinuous castings. These normally have inadequate microstructures and properties, mainly due to porosity and sometimes poor reinforcement wetting.

When the final product has a uniform shape, there are several processes for a later thermomechanical consolidation (principally hot rolling and extrusion). However if subsequent non-uniform sections are necessary, then it would be essential to develop some conventional forging processes, such as open and closed die forging.

A significant problem, for MMC forging, is the metal matrix stiffness originating from the presence of ceramic particles. This causes an important change in the working conditions, provided that the matrix plastic deformation is considerably lowered by the anchoring effect produced by the reinforcement.

Figure 1. Compression test pieces, before and after deformation.

2. FORGEABILITY

The forgeability of any material could be defined as its capacity to suffer great plastic deformations without cracks or defects formation, either external or internal.

For a specific material, the resistance to hot deformation depends on (1):

- Amount of deformation.
- Deformation rate.
- Material temperature.
- Geometric shape coefficient (this can be defined as a maximum equivalent diameter/height rate after the application of a force, that is, after a deformation).
- Physical and chemical composition of the material.

2.1. Types of Forgeability Test

There are several methods to evaluate the forgeability, the most common being:

A) Tensile test: The test piece can be uniform section or notched bar (2) at various temperatures. In these tests the normal responses to evaluate the forgeability are the reduction of area and elongation after breaking (3).

B) Compression test: The test piece can also be uniform or notched (2). In this case the parameters are the test temperature and the strain rate and the most usual representations are graphs of forging pressure or forging load versus upset reduction, with the forging temperature as a parameter (4).

C) Relative forgeability: This experience consists of relating the data obtained through testing different materials. For this, it is necessary to assign an arbitrary reference unit and then to relate the obtained results to this unit. The tests carried out for that could be the normal compression test and so the related response could be the absorbed energy (4). Another test is twisting: In this case the parameter to relate is the number of twists until the test piece breaks up (2). In the graphs representing the relative forgeability, the higher the number obtained the better the deformability of the material.

Figure 2. Absorbed energy, forging a 2014/Al₂O_{3p} MMC.

3. TEST MATERIAL

All the tests, for this study, were carried out with the purchased MMC 2014/Al₂O_{3p}. The material was manufactured by the DC (discontinuous casting) process. The alumina particles have a size range of 10/15 μm, with a volume fraction of 15%. The dimensions of the composite billets were 178 mm in diameter and 500 mm in length. The chemical composition of the matrix is exhibited in Table 1.

Table 1. Chemical composition of aluminium alloy 2014.

Cu	Si	Mn	Mg	Fe	Cr	Zn	Ti	Al
4.38	0.79	0.80	0.41	0.07	0.003	0.03	0.02	balance

Figure 3. Forgeability map, forging a 2014/Al₂O_{3p} MMC.

This alloy has a medium forgeability, in comparison with other aluminium alloys (4) and it seems to have a good wettability with the alumina particles, which could be very interesting with regard to the necessary fiber-matrix boundary strength, for a good transfer of stresses during the deformation.

4. FORGEABILITY TESTS CARRIED OUT

We think that the most appropriate test to obtain the forgeability of any material is the compression test, because in it the alloy flows as in the forging process.

The tests were performed changing the working temperature, the strain rate and total deformation. The first parameter was chosen according to the forging temperatures range of a 2014 alloy. Five strain rates and four total deformations were chosen for each temperature (see Table 2). Tests were done combining these three parameters depending on the results of the preceding tests.

Table 2. Parameters for the forging experiment design.

Temperature Test (°C)	Strain Rate (s ⁻¹)	Total Deformation (%)
430	0.5	10
	1.0	20
	1.5	30
	2.5	40
	5.0	
500	0.5	10
	1.0	20
	1.5	30
	2.5	40

It was decided for the test pieces to have the dimensions of 14 mm diameter and 21 mm height, as shown in Figure 1. The tests were carried out in an INSTRON 8501 testing machine, which has a furnace to heat the test pieces.

The test procedure was:

- Before testing the material, it was solution heat treated at 500 °C, for 4 hours, followed by a quenching in cold water.
- In the test, once the test temperature was reached it was maintained for 10 minutes, before the test performance, in order to allow a good temperature homogeneity.

The response in those tests was the formation of cracks on the greatest diameter of the barrel, and the energy necessary to deform the material. See Figure 1, for some test pieces with different deformation degrees.

x50

Figure 4. Forging cracks, formed at equatorial zone of a test piece, after compression.

5. FORGEABILITY GRAPHICS

In order to have a good interpretation of data obtained in the tests we have produced two graphs:

5.1. Absorbed Energy

In this case, we have plotted the absorbed energy versus the forging temperature. We chose this representation because it takes into account the deformation suffered by the test piece, when calculating the work done by the press.

As shown in Figure 2, The necessary work to forge the MMC increases as both the deformation rate and the total deformation increases. We can also see that the work done to deform a 10% is lesser than the necessary for a 20% deformation and so for a 30 and 40%

pass. On the other hand it is also clear that the higher the temperature and the lower the deformation rate, the easier the forging.

x50
Figure 5. Shrinking porosity, bad particle distribution and the presence of some cracks due to lack of base alloy, in the original material.

5.2. Forgeability Map

We consider that a graph such as that of Figure 2 does not give a good enough idea about the forgeability of any particular material. It gives a notion of how easy it is to forge this material and how much force the press must have to deform a block of a given size. So we have prepared a forgeability map taking into account the surface defects appearing on the test sample after deformation. In this way, we have produced a map (Figure 3), with the total deformation on the X axis and the deformation rate on the Y axis, using the temperature as a parameter. The map shows two different zones. The left one has a good forgeability and the tests carried out with these conditions have not presented any surface defects. On the other hand, the forging parameters on the right side produced defective pieces.

It follows from Figure 3 that as the total deformation and the deformation rate increase, surface defects are more likely to appear.

The forgeability map is therefore the best graph to show the real forging conditions and to apply in normal MMC pieces configuration.

6. METALLURGICAL STUDY

The purchased material was high in porosity and had many slag inclusions, so it was necessary to forge the round billets before the tests. In this way, the composite was deformed with a reduction of 3:1 and the test results whose samples had a crack originated by a slag inclusion were rejected.

x50

Figure 6. Particle distribution, in a longitudinal section of a forged MMC.

A macroscopic study was made to examine crack morphology, macrostructure and particle distribution.

Figure 4 shows two typical ductile cracks, after deformation, with inter-granular growth. It was considered that for all the tests pieces in which these cracks appeared the used parameters were wrong, and the corresponding points were situated in the non forging zone of Figure 3.

A typical shrinking porosity is shown in Figure 5. This photograph was taken of the original material, before forging, and it also exhibits bad particle distribution and the presence of some cracks, due to lack of base alloy because of the particle agglomeration.

If we observe this structure after forging (Figure 6), we can see the particle orientation and some band formation, but in any case, now the distribution has been enhanced by the deformation effect.

When any material is deformed by a force applied on two parallel faces, leaving free the whole lateral surface, not all the section is deformed in the same way. The fact is that there are two cones beside the constricting surfaces, that have very little or no deformation (see Figure 7), but just between the two vertices the maximum deformation happens. The lateral zones are deformed and displaced outwards. In this figure it is also possible to see, at the bottom right, a large slag inclusion.

7. CONCLUSIONS

From the above described the following conclusions are consequent in the forging of 2014/Al₂O_{3p} MMC:

- * As the total deformation and/or the deformation rate increase:
 - Surface defects are more likely to appear.
 - The work necessary to forge increases (and so the force).

- It is possible to raise the deformation rate, but then it would be necessary to decrease the total deformation, in each pass.
- To develop a forging procedure, for this particular material, it will be necessary to choose the pass parameters inside the forging zone of the forgeability map.

* The purchased material was very porous and for its later use it will be necessary to forge it. There were also a lot of slag inclusions, that make this composite unable to guarantee the soundness, and also the properties of the pieces to be made.

x5

Figure 7. Different deformation zones and a slag inclusion (right bottom).

References

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